

5.4 SCOPUS数据的可视化分析

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李杰, 陈超美. CiteSpace科技文本挖掘及可视化(第四版)[M]. 首都经济贸易大学出版社. 2025.

李杰科学网博客: <http://blog.sciencenet.cn/u/jerrycueb>

开放科学计量学学习平台: <https://www.metamatrix.cn/home>

The longer you can look back, the farther you can look forward (回顾历史越久远, 展望未来就越深远)。

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Document title

1 Avatars, people, and virtual worlds: Foundations for research in metaverses *Open Access* Dav Ow D, :

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2 Making real money in virtual worlds: MMORPGs and emerging business opportunities, challenges and ethical implications in metaverses *Open Access* Pap Bou

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3 Second life and the new generation of virtual worlds Kun Kim Kim

3

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 Set alert

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- 2020 (15) >

Documents Secondary documents

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1 All Text export Download

- Select all
- Select page

1 research in metaverses
Open Access

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2 Making real money in virtual worlds
emerging business opportunities, of
ethical implications in metaverses
Open Access

[View abstract](#) [View at Publisher](#)

3 Second life and the new generation

SCOPUS

Export document settings

You have chosen to export 441 documents

Select your method of export

MENDELEY ExLibris RefWorks SciVal **1** RIS Format CSV BibTeX Plain Text

EndNote, Reference Manager Excel ASCII in HTML

What information do you want to export?

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citation information	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bibliographical information	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Abstract & keywords	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Funding details	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other information
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Author(s)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Affiliations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Abstract	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Number	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tradenames & manufacturers
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Author(s) ID	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Serial identifiers (e.g. ISSN)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Author keywords	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acronym	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Accession numbers & chemicals
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Document title	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PubMed ID	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Index keywords	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sponsor	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Conference information
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Year	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Publisher		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Funding text	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2 Include references
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EID	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Editor(s)			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Source title	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Language of original document			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> volume, issue, pages	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Correspondence address			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citation count	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Abbreviated source title			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Source & document type				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Publication Stage				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DOI				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Open Access				

Cancel Export

SCOPUS

名称	修改日期	类型
scopus.ris	2022/6/28 10:01	risfile

```
scopus.ris
1 TY - JOUR
2 TI - Avatars, people, and virtual worlds: Foundations for research in metaverses
3 T2 - Journal of the Association for Information Systems
4 J2 - J. Assoc. Inf. Syst.
5 VL - 10
6 IS - 2
7 SP - 90
8 EP - 117
9 PY - 2009
10 DO - 10.17705/1jais.00183
11 SN - 15369323 (ISSN)
12 AU - Davis, A.
13 AU - Murphy, J.
14 AU - Owens, D.
15 AU - Khazanchi, D.
16 AU - Zigurs, I.
17 AD - University of Nebraska at Omaha, United States
18 AB - Metaverses are immersive three-dimensional virtual worlds in which people interact. The ubiquitous availability of high speed Internet access has spurred enormous interest in global virtual collaboration. These environments have potential for richer, more engaging virtual worlds for virtual team collaboration. We develop a conceptual model for research capabilities, (4) behaviors, and (5) outcomes. We present an in-depth characterization of interaction and its outcomes. Example propositions and a discussion of key issues and challenges are provided. © 2009, by the Association for Information Systems.
19 KW - Collaboration
20 KW - Metaverses
21 KW - Virtual teams
22 KW - Virtual worlds
23 KW - Interactive computer graphics
24 KW - Software agents
25 KW - Three dimensional computer graphics
26 KW - Virtual reality
27 KW - Collaboration
28 KW - Emergent interactions
29 KW - Metaverses
30 KW - New technological platform
31 KW - Three-dimensional virtual world
32 KW - Virtual collaboration
33 KW - Virtual team
34 KW - Virtual worlds
35 KW - Behavioral research
36 PB - Association for Information Systems
37 N1 - Cited By :191
38 N1 - Export Date: 28 June 2022
39 M3 - Article
40 DB - Scopus
41 LA - English
42 N1 - Correspondence Address: Davis, A.; University of Nebraska at OmahaUnited States;
43 N1 - References: Bailenson, J.N., Beall, A.C., Blascovich, J., Gaze and task performance
44 Bailenson, J.N., Swinth, K., Hoyt, C., Persky, S., The independent and interactive effects
```

SCOPUS

名称	修改日期	类型
data	2022/6/28 10:02	文件夹
data scopus	2022/6/28 10:03	文件夹
project	2022/6/28 10:03	文件夹
scopus.ris	2022/6/28 10:01	risfile

名称	修改日期	类型
download_1-441.ris	2022/6/28 10:01	risfile

新建了data, data scopus和project文件夹。
其中data和project文件夹为空文件夹; data scopus中为所下载的scopus原始数据。所下载的数据为RIS格式, 并命名为download_1-441.

CITESPACE

Check the Connection to MySQL@localhost

A problem encountered when attempting to connect your MySQL at localhost.

1. Make sure your MySQL server is on.
2. Make sure the following username and password in C:\Users\dell.citespace\mysql.ini are correct.
host: null
user: null
pass: null

2

Update my login credentials Skip MySQL for now

CiteSpace: Data Processing Utilities

MySQL WOS Scopus Dimensions CNKI CSSCI MAG CSV PubMed

Database Project Edit

3

Current Project

Project Name Count Records Select a query here ...

Warning: Queries with * are time-consuming. Execute them with the Search button.

Create a New Project

Input Directory C:\Users\dell Browse WOS Import

Text Analysis

Term Extraction from Title and Abstract Fields

words: min 2 max 4 Extract Phrases Extract Verbs Summarize

Statistical Association Test

Phrase freq > 1 Show Distributions p-level 0.01 Log-Likelihood Show Graph

SQL Query and Results

```
SELECT count(*) FROM articles
```

Results of your SQL query will appear here.

Execute Query Save Results Save As WoS Save As CSV Plot SQL Results of (Year, Value)

CiteSpace 6.1.R2 (64-bit) Advanced - (c) 2003-2022 Chaomei Chen - Home: C:\Users\dell

File Projects Data Visualization Overlay Maps Analytics Network Text Preferences Tutorials Help Donate

Web of Science Import/Export **1**

Projects

New Demo 1: Terrorism (1996-2003) More Actions ...

Project Home: C:\Users\dell.citespace\Examples\WoS\Terrorism1990-200

Data Directory: C:\Users\dell.citespace\Examples\WoS\Terrorism1990-200

GO! Stop Reset JVM Memory 1024 (MB) Used 9 %

Space Status

Process Reports

Time Slicing

From 1993 JAN To 2003 DEC #Years Per Slice 1

Text Processing

Term Source

Title Abstract Author Keywords (DE) Keywords Plus (ID)

Term Type

Noun Phrases Burst Terms Detect Bursts Entropy

Node Types

Author Institution Country Term Keyword Source Category

Reference Cited Author Cited Journal

Links

Strength Cosine Scope Within Slices

Selection Criteria

g-index Top N Top N% Thresholds Citations Usage180 Usage2013

The selection uses a modified g-index in each slice: $g^2 \leq k \sum_{i \leq g} c_i, k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

To include more or fewer nodes, increase or decrease the scale factor k = 25

Pruning Visualization

Pruning

Pathfinder Pruning sliced networks

Minimum Spanning Tree Pruning the merged network

CITESPACE

The screenshot shows the CiteSpace Data Processing Utilities window. At the top, there are tabs for MySQL, WOS, Scopus, Dimensions, CNKI, CSSCI, MAG, CSV, and PubMed. The main area is titled "Scopus Data Conversion" with a date of 5/19/2022. Under the "Usage" section, it describes "Step 1: Download data from Scopus" and "Step 2: Use CiteSpace to Convert the data format". The "Data Directories" section contains two text boxes: "Input Directory" with the path "D:\桌面\SCOPUS\data scopus" and "Output Directory" with the path "D:\桌面\SCOPUS\data". Each text box has a "Browse" button to its right, with red arrows pointing to them. Below the text boxes are two buttons: "Scopus (RIS) -> WoS" and "Scopus (Tab Delimited) -> WoS". At the bottom, a status bar shows "441 records converted from download_1-441.ris", "Total References: 14467", and "Valid References: 13613 (94.0%)".

D:\桌面\SCOPUS\data scopus

D:\桌面\SCOPUS\data

441 records converted from download_1-441.ris

Total References: 14467

Valid References: 13613 (94.0%)

CITESPACE

CITESPACE

New Project

Title To compute uncertainties, use the same project name in MySQL as well.

Project Home

Data Directory

Data Source WoS Scopus Lens MAG CNKI/WanFang CSCD CSSCI PubMed

Preferred Language English Chinese

SO Filter: SC Filter:

Alias List (on/off)	<input type="text" value="on"/>	Exclusion List (on/off)	<input type="text" value="on"/>
Export Space (on/off)	<input type="text" value="off"/>	Export Abstracts (Time Consuming) (on/off)	<input type="text" value="on"/>
Export Matrices (csv) (off/on)	<input type="text" value="off"/>	Enable JDIC (on/off)	<input type="text" value="on"/>
Save Merged Slice (off/on)	<input type="text" value="off"/>	Phrase/Keyword: Minimum Words (2)	<input type="text" value="2"/>
Phrase/Keyword: Maximum Words (4)	<input type="text" value="4"/>	Burst Term Threshold (0.00)	<input type="text" value="0.00"/>
Maximum GML Node Label Length (8)	<input type="text" value="8"/>	CTSA (1-Disciplines, 2-Sciences) (1)	<input type="text" value="1"/>
Include GP (Group Author) (off/on)	<input type="text" value="off"/>	Include ED (Editors) (off/on)	<input type="text" value="off"/>
Node Degree Weighted (true)	<input type="text" value="true"/>	Look Back Years (LBY)(-1:unlimited)	<input type="text" value="-1"/>
Link Retaining Factor (LRF)(*N; -1:unlimited)	<input type="text" value="3"/>	Percentage of Nodes to Label (%)	<input type="text" value="1.0"/>
Maximum Links Per Node (L/N) (-1:unlimited)	<input type="text" value="10"/>	TopN = {n f(n)≥e}	<input type="text" value="1.0"/>
Filter Refs By Intrinsic Citations	<input type="text" value="on"/>	Concept Tree Home	<input type="text" value="C:\Users\cc345\citespace"/>
Use Authors' Fullnames	<input type="text" value="on"/>	Dimensions Endpoint	<input type="text" value="https://app.dimensions.ai/"/>

Normalize Citations Global Check

Description

CITESPACE

时间切片设置

SCOPUS中的数据时间趋势

 A test version of the search results page is available. We are working on a new results page.

441 document results

TITLE-ABS-KEY (metaverse*)

 Set alert

Search within results...

Refine results

Open Access

 Analyze search results

All RIS export Download

Document title

**CITES
PACE**

1995-2022

Visible	Count	Central...	Year	Cited References
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<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.00	2013	Dionisio JDN, 2013, 3D VI...
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Control Panel

Colormap Burstness Search Clusters

Labels Layout Views

Keyword | Term | Overlay Labels

By Degree Show Frequency

Threshold: 10

Font Size: 15

Node Size: 10

Node Labels

By Citation Show Frequency

Threshold: 2

Font Size: 4

Node Size: 5

Link Labels

Show Link Labels Show Link Strengths

Font Size: 8

Cluster Labels

Threshold: 0

Font Size: 0

Show Cluster Labels Over Time

Max Length: 55

Minimizing Overlaps

Cluster Labels Node Labels

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<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	13	0.00	2012	COMPUTERS IN HUMAN ...
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<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.00	2012	JOURNAL OF CONSUME...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.00	2010	COMPUTER
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2022	FRONTIERS IN PSYCHOL...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2021	J BUS RES
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2022	LOOKING TO THE FUTURE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2018	J VIRTUAL WORLDS RES
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2013	JOURNAL OF RETAILING ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2021	MIS QUARTERLY
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2021	INTERNATIONAL JOURN...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2009	@ SYNTHETIC WORLDS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2010	COMMUN ACM
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2022	A METAVERSE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2021	METAVERSE FOR SOCIAL...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2021	ACM TRANS GRAPH
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2021	ELECTRONICS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2012	MAKING REAL MONEY IN ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2021	SCI REP
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2021	BEHAVIOUR & INFORMAT...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2022	IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2013	NEW YORK
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2021	JOURNAL OF MANAGEME...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2021	VIRTUAL EXPERIMENTS I...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2010	@ METAVERSE ROADMA...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2010	IEEE COMPUTER GRAPH...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2021	EDUCATIONAL APPLICAT...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	2021	APPLIED SCIENCES
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	2021	IS AUGMENTED REALITY ...

期刊共被引

Control Panel

Colormap Burstness Search Clusters

Labels Layout Views

Keyword | Term | Overlay Labels

By Degree Show Frequency

Threshold 10

Font Size 15

Node Size 10

Node Labels

By Citation Show Frequency

Threshold 6

Font Size 3

Node Size 5

Link Labels

Show Link Labels Show Link Strengths

Font Size 8

Cluster Labels

Threshold 0

Font Size 0

Show Cluster Labels Over Time

Max Length 55

Minimizing Overlaps

Cluster Labels Node Labels

CiteSpace, v. 6.1.R2 (64-bit) Advanced
 June 28, 2022 at 2:05:11 PM CST
 Scopus: D:\桌面\SCOPUS\data
 Timespan: 2002-2022 (Slice Length=3)
 Selection Criteria: g-index (k=25), LRF=3.0, L/N=10, LBY=-1, e=1.0
 Network: N=350, E=840 (Density=0.0138)
 Largest CC: 288 (82%)
 Nodes Labeled: 1.0%
 Pruning: None
 Modularity Q=0.7616
 Weighted Mean Silhouette S=0.9005
 Harmonic Mean(Q, S)=0.8253

The Link Strength is filtered by PMI of 0.75. The maximum value of PMI is 1.00. The higher the PMI, the fewer links will be retained because only links with strengths greater than the threshold will survive.

Visible	Count	Central...	Year	Authors Institutions Cou...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	75	0.00	2002	UNITED STATES
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	51	0.00	2012	CHINA
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	48	0.00	2010	SOUTH KOREA
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	45	0.00	2007	UNITED KINGDOM
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	30	0.00	2008	JAPAN
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	19	0.00	2010	TURKEY
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	17	0.00	2006	ITALY
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	17	0.00	2010	AYITER E
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	16	0.00	2009	SPAIN
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	16	0.00	2003	ANONYMOUS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	14	0.00	2007	GERMANY
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.00	2007	CANADA
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	12	0.00	2010	Sabanci University
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.00	2009	FRANCE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.00	2006	BRAZIL
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	8	0.00	2022	FINLAND
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2009	AUSTRALIA
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2017	KIM S
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7	0.00	2008	NETHERLANDS
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2022	INDIA
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2022	WANG F
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2011	THAWONMAS R
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2021	PARK S
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2010	AUSTRIA
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6	0.00	2006	Department of Computer ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	2010	BARRY D
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	2022	TAIWAN
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	2011	LEE S
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	2022	LEE H
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	0.00	2022	UNITED ARAB EMIRATES
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2022	SWITZERLAND
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2022	WIEDERHOLD B
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2009	KHAZANCHI D
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2015	GREECE
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2013	COLOMBIA
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2010	KANEMATSU H
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2022	LI Y
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2022	State Key Laboratory for M...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2011	Intelligent Computer Enter...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2012	FUKUMURA Y
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2009	CHEN Y
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2012	College of Information Sci...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2022	LEE J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2013	SWEDEN
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2022	DENMARK
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2011	BELGIUM
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4	0.00	2021	The Chinese University of ...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2002	JAYNES C
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2017	PORTUGAL
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2008	BOURLAKIS M
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2011	OSSWALD T
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2022	LIU Y
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2011	BRENGMAN M
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2022	SERBIA
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2022	WANG J
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2022	WANG Y
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3	0.00	2022	WANG X

CiteSpace, v. 6.1.R2 (64-bit) Advanced
 June 28, 2022 at 2:12:19 PM CST
 Scopus: D:\桌面\SCOPUS\data
 Timespan: 2002-2022 (Slice Length=1)
 Selection Criteria: g-index (l=25), LRF=3.0, L/N=10, LBY=-1, e=1.0
 Network: N=457, E=966 (Density=0.0083)
 Largest CC: 159 (34%)
 Nodes Labeled: 1.0%
 Pruning: None
 Modularity Q=0.876
 Weighted Mean Silhouette S=0.9738
 Harmonic Mean(Q, S)=0.9223

CITESPACE学习文献

李杰, 陈超美. CiteSpace科技文本挖掘及可视化(第四版)[M]. 首都经济贸易大学出版社. 2025.

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科学计量学理论与工具视频 MOOC for Scientometrics Theories and Tools

开放科学计量学视频号

什么是科学计量学 (AI生成)

CiteSpace
CiteSpace理论与实践
(主讲人：陈超美、李杰)
链接1 链接2 链接3

陈超美 科学网博客

李杰 科学网博客

武夷山 科学网博客
(课外学习推荐)

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文献计量学的局限性

库恩的科学革命

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第一届MKD珍贵视频

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开放科学计量学学习平台: <https://www.metamatrix.cn/mooc>

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